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Print light synthesis of Ni catalysts for CO₂RR

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Abstract

The electroreduction of CO₂ into valuable chemicals provides a sustainable pathway to mitigate GHG emissions while addressing pressing energy and environmental challenges. This study focuses on a scalable and cost-effective process for fabricating cathodes with Ni-based catalysts to convert CO₂ into CO by reactive inkjet printing. Metal precursor-based inks were formulated for the process and printed using a custom-built inkjet printer. Post-printing using a xenon flash lamp was employed to reduce the nickel metal precursor into active catalyst structures. The full process is called print light synthesis (**Figure 1**). This method reduces energy consumption and production time compared to conventional high-temperature synthesis. SEM/EDX and XRD analysis confirmed uniform catalyst deposition and predominant presence of metallic Ni after the print light synthesis process. Microwave plasma atomic emission spectrometry (MP-AES) analysis evidenced a conversion rate of approximately 80% from nickel precursor into metallic Ni. Electrochemical characterizations, including cyclic voltammetry and chronoamperometry coupled to gas chromatography analysis, confirmed the efficiency of the synthesized Ni/C PLS catalyst (0.5 mg_{Ni}/cm²) for selective CO₂ conversion into CO, with a faradaic efficiency of 64% at -0.75V (vs RHE).

Figure 1: Schematic of the print light synthesis process.

Introduction

The electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide (CO₂RR) is a promising strategy for addressing two of the most critical challenges nowadays: (i) climate change and (ii) the sustainable production of fuels and chemicals. CO₂ recycling into valuable products through electroreduction provides a pathway to close the carbon loop, potentially achieving carbon neutrality when coupled with renewable electricity sources. Moreover, CO₂RR operates under relatively mild conditions, is compatible with existing chemical infrastructure, and supports the development of decentralized production systems, making it a scalable and economically attractive solution for a circular carbon economy. As research progresses, advancements in catalyst design and reactor engineering are required to further improve the efficiency and selectivity of CO₂ electroreduction into added-value compounds/fuels.

1. Scientific Approach

The electrochemical reduction of CO₂ can be controlled mainly by the catalyst type and applied potential, providing selectivity to a desired added-value compound/fuel. The CO₂RR can generate several products such as formic acid (HCOOH), carbon monoxide (CO), methanol (CH₃OH), ethanol (C₂H₅OH), methane (CH₄), ethylene (C₂H₄) and other hydrocarbons and alcohols. [1] Precious metals such as gold and silver are commonly employed as catalysts for CO₂RR, however their high price and scarcity are limiting factors for applications in practical devices. In this scenario, non-noble metals such as iron (Fe), nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), etc., have gained significant attention as cost-effective and earth-abundant alternatives for CO₂RR. [2] In particular, nickel (Ni) shows to be effective for converting CO₂ to carbon monoxide (CO), which is well known as a key precursor for syngas and chemical synthesis. [3-5] However, despite their significant advantages there are still several challenges in terms of improving their selectivity, activity, and long-term durability for CO₂RR. Therefore, continued advancements in material design, such as nanostructures, nitrogen-doping, and support engineering, are key to improve the performance of the non-noble catalysts for practical CO₂ electroreduction applications. [6-9]

The conventional methods to synthesize active catalysts for CO₂ are still complex and challenging since multiple steps are required, for example M-N-C from single-atom catalysts (M = non-noble metals), requires not only a long time for the complete synthesis but also additional cleaning steps with strong acids, toxic solvents, and many steps of heating at high temperatures at 700-1000°C (reactors, oven, dryers, etc.), which makes challenging the scale up of the CO₂ electrolyzer technology. In this context, a new approach recently introduced using a flash light irradiation from a powerful xenon flash lamp could be a promising alternative, since it can drive thermal processes reaching high temperatures (up to 2850 °C) during a very short residence time (micro- to milliseconds), [10] which can likely minimize the catalyst nanoparticle growth/agglomeration and likely maximize the single-atom catalyst sites as recently illustrated by few works. [11-14] These findings evidence the potential of this technology for catalyst synthesis that could be potentially applied for several applications such as fabrication of active and selective cathodes for CO₂ electrolyzers.

Therefore, this study aims to introduce a new process for fabrication of cathodes for CO₂RR, ideally from non-noble metals, directly from commercially available gas diffusion layers (containing MPL with porous carbon) using a new approach called print light synthesis.

2. Experiments

The employed approach involves formulating an inkjet ink from nickel nitrate (25mg_{Ni}/mL) from water and ethanol-based formulation, which was printed onto a commercial gas diffusion layer, a carbon cloth substrate coated with a microporous layer (thickness 400µm, carbon black loading 2.5 mg/cm², PTFE 20-30wt%), using an industrial printhead (Epson S3200) to create a metal precursor layer of 0.5mg_{Ni}/cm². This layer was then exposed to flash light irradiation (under Argon atmosphere) from a 16kW xenon flash lamp (Excelitas NobleLight, Germany) for 150 ms with a total energy density of 400 J/cm², inducing the reduction of the nickel salt into small metal nickel nanoparticles. This entire process was denoted Print Light Synthesis (PLS) and the synthesized catalyst as Ni/C PLS. [13] The gas diffusion electrode containing Ni nanoparticles were characterized by XRD and SEM/EDX. The Ni loadings before and after the flash light irradiation process were quantified by Microwave plasma atomic emission spectrometry (MP-AES). The catalytic performance for CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR) was evaluated using standard electrochemical techniques, in a gas-tight two-compartment cell separated by a Nafion 211 membrane in a 0.5 M KHCO₃ electrolyte with CO₂-saturated in the cathode side, combined with gas chromatography analysis to quantify the products from CO₂RR.

3. Results

The synthesized Ni/C PLS electrode was initially cleaned several times with water to dissolve/remove possible remaining nickel nitrate salt, afterwards MP-AES analysis was performed and evidenced a conversion rate of approximately 80% into metallic Ni, the estimated conversion rate was calculated from a triplicate of Ni electrodes with and without post-treatment by flash light irradiation. **Figure 2** shows SEM/EDX images of the Ni/C PLS synthesized by print light synthesis. The images show a uniform Ni dispersion over the microporous carbon layer with small Ni nanoparticle sizes with almost no large agglomerations. XRD diffractograms of the Ni/C PLS and Bare GDL presented in **Figure 3** show typical crystallography diffraction peaks at 44.6, 51.9, 76.46 attributed to the Ni (111), (200) and (220) planes, respectively, (PDF #04-0850), which is attributed to the metallic Ni.[15] In addition, the absence of XRD peaks from nickel oxide, nickel nitrite, nickel carbide and/or unconverted nickel nitrate salt, suggests the majority formation of metallic nickel by using the PLS approach. Therefore, print light synthesis is a promising approach that successfully synthesized Ni nanoparticles directly on a gas diffusion layer (GDL).

Figure 2: SEM/EDX images of the Ni/C PLS synthesized by print light synthesis.

Figure 3: X-ray diffractograms of the Ni/C PLS and Bare GDL.

The catalytic performance of the synthesized Ni/C PLS was initially investigated by cyclic voltammetry (CV), using a standard three electrode electrochemical cell, in KOH 1 M electrolyte saturated with argon at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ as shown in **Figure 4a**. The CV profile presents typical Ni redox peaks at 1.2-1.45V (vs RHE), the anodic peak shows the Ni oxidation state from Ni(II) to Ni(III), where b-Ni(OH)₂ is oxidized to b-NiOOH and the cathodic peak shows the reduction process, this evidence the formation of active Ni catalyst sites by using PLS method. The catalytic performance of Ni/C PLS for CO₂ electroreduction was evaluated by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV). The LSV curves presented in **Figure 4b** showed higher current density at more positive onset potential for CO₂-saturated electrolyte compared to Argon, which evidences the occurrence of CO₂ electroreduction. Gas chromatography analysis coupled with electrochemical tests at constant potential electrolysis were performed at different potentials for 30 min to quantify the products from CO₂RR.[16] As illustrated by **Figure 4c** the CO₂ conversion into CO starts at -0.6V (vs RHE) and shows a maximum faradaic efficiency of CO at -0.75V (vs RHE) with 64% and current density of 6mA cm⁻² (**Figure 4d**), at more cathodic potentials and current densities H₂ production is likely favored due to the CO₂ mass transport limitations, however the FE_{CO} could be further improved by using a flow cell configuration. Overall, Ni/C PLS catalyst demonstrated a promising activity and selectivity for CO₂RR to CO, however, further PLS improvements will continue to be explored in order to achieve a higher faradaic selectivity for CO (>90%) as already reported by previous works,[3,5] that typically apply nickel single-atom catalysts (Ni SACs) supported on nitrogen-doped carbon (NC) materials, however from complex and time consuming synthesis protocols, on the other hand PLS has the advantage to be a faster and simple approach. Therefore, this innovative approach (print light synthesis) can manufacture active gas diffusion electrodes (potentially from different metals, alloys and/or SACs) for electrochemical CO₂ reduction, paving the way for more sustainable and efficient methods to address global carbon emissions and create value-added products.

Figure 4: (a) Cyclic voltammetry of Ni/C PLS in KOH 1M saturated with Argon at scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹. (b) Linear sweep voltammetry of Ni/C PLS in KHCO₃ 0.5M saturated with Argon and CO₂ at scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹. (c) Faradaic efficiency of CO and H₂ from CO₂RR catalyzed by Ni/C PLS at different potentials after 30 minutes of electrolysis in CO₂-saturated KHCO₃ 0.5M aqueous solution and (d) Faradaic efficiency of CO from CO₂RR catalyzed by Ni/C PLS at different current densities after 30 minutes of electrolysis in CO₂-saturated KHCO₃ 0.5M aqueous solution.

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